

Effect of Ownership Structure on Financial Reporting Quality of Listed Oil and Gas Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

The study conducted a fixed-effect regression analysis based on Hausman specification to examine the relationship between ownership structure and financial reporting quality in a sample of oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The study used a longitudinal research design; the population of this study consists of the 9 listed oil and Gas on the floor of the Nigeria Exchange Group as of 2022, and the census samples are to be used to sample for data from their annual reports for the period 2013 to 2022. The sample size became the population of the study since it was relatively small. Secondary data was extracted from the annual report of the listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The study utilizes multiple panel regression with the aid of STATA 17 to analyses the data. The results revealed several significant findings. Firstly, managerial ownership was found to have a negative impact on financial reporting quality, suggesting that higher levels of managerial ownership were associated with lower-quality reporting. Secondly, foreign ownership did not show a significant relationship with financial reporting quality, suggesting that foreign ownership had no discernible impact on reporting practices. On the other hand, institutional ownership and ownership concentration were positively associated with financial reporting quality, indicating that higher levels of both institutional ownership and ownership concentration were linked to higher-quality reporting. The study, therefore, concluded that ownership structure has a significant effect on the financial reporting quality of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The study, therefore, recommends that it should enhance Corporate Governance Practices; given the negative impact of managerial ownership on financial reporting quality, it is important for firms to strengthen corporate governance mechanisms. This could include implementing stricter monitoring and oversight mechanisms, ensuring independent board representation, and aligning the interests of managers with those of shareholders through appropriate incentive structures.

Keywords: Financial reporting quality, Managerial ownership, Managerial ownership, Institutional ownership, Managerial ownership

Introduction

The global corporate scandals and the collapses of several major organizations, which have affected most of the world in the past twenty (20) years, including Nigeria, have pushed up the demand for high financial reporting quality. These turbulent events (failures or collapses of some of these firms) have dramatically highlighted the importance of credible, high-quality audits to investors and creditors in Nigeria as they enhance the degree of confidence and reliability to enable them to make investment decisions. However, the collapse of major firms, on one hand, was attributable to the poor performance of the board of directors, indicating the inability of the boards to carry out effective and efficient monitoring of top management. On the other hand, it was attributable to poor financial reporting quality, showing that the auditors lack the courage to express qualified opinions when errors/misstatements are found in the financial statement prepared by the company management. As a result of financial scandals in major corporations, financial reporting quality has gained increased concerns. The aftermath of these scandals has led to the identification of a perceived expectation gap in financial reporting quality as many users of audited financial statements have different expectations of the audit function culminating to a call for changes in the auditing profession to ensure improved financial reporting quality.

However, in the past, considerable studies have been conducted disparately on the determinants of financial reporting quality with mixed and inconclusive results in variables measurement or methodologies applied. Thus, Siregar (2012), Ibrani et al; (2020), Yang et al; (2018), Abbasi (2019). Aobdia (2018), Khasharmeh and Joseph, (2017), Mardijuwono et al; (2021) and Zureigat (2011) found a nexus between those variables that determined financial reporting quality.

A common feature with all these studies is that each of them has considered corporate characteristics, audit attributes, board attributes, et cetera disparately on determinants of financial reporting quality, and none of them has considered the synergy of combining some of the available corporate governance attributes that could be used to predict and explain financial reporting quality on firms to find out what synergetic impact of the combination of two or more corporate governance attributes could jointly have on a phenomenon such as determinants of financial reporting quality in research. This needs to be tested. This study thus tries to examine various corporate governance attributes to explain financial reporting quality using a multiple panel single equation model.

Early studies have also lightly touched upon the issue of determinants of financial reporting variables affecting financial reporting quality in firms. However, they have neither produced sufficient results to provide a clear picture of the relationship nor have they adequately addressed the issue of inconsistent results, providing no conclusive evidence of whether the relationship is positive, negative or neutral (Abu et al; (2018), Abbasi (2019), Aobdia (2018), Enofe et al; (2013), Ibrani et al; (2020), Khasharmeh and Joseph, (2017), Mardijuwono et al; (2021), Siregar (2012), Yang et al; (2018) and Zureigat (2011); thereby necessitating further research to add to existing knowledge.

Again, a few studies have investigated the determinants of financial reporting quality in Nigeria focused on banking and financial subsectors. However, the concept of determinants of financial reporting quality, though a fledging development in Nigeria, transcends across different sectors,

the sectorial peculiarity of oil and gas firms is not being given due attention by many of the research, and even fewer are specifically from other countries (Chang and Zhang, (2015), Ezhilarasi & Kabra, (2017), Gabriel (2015), Hamad et al; (2020), Masud et al; (2018), Nguyen and Nguyen (2020) and Shahgholian (2018) from Pakistan, Malaysian or Egyptian perspective. Their results are peculiar to their countries and have little application to Nigeria because of differences in economic and political environments (Oyedokun, Oyedokun, & Oyedokun, 2025). Hence, there is a need to conduct research in this area with Nigerian terrain focusing on methodological differences by formulating a model for various determinants studied to ascertain their synergetic effect on the dependent variable in a single equation multiple regression model.

This study is therefore motivated by the need to fill the gap in variables robustness and sub-sectorial analysis lacking in many studies, the sectorial peculiarity of oil and gas firms, external validity, and timing differences by examining the determinants of financial reporting quality, (structural determinants of financial reporting quality of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no study has thoroughly incorporated such a combination of corporate governance characteristics to explain financial reporting quality using a robust methodological approach.

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the effect of ownership structure on financial reporting. Quality of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Concept of Financial Reporting Quality

Financial reporting quality is a report presented based on the company's condition, which can decrease due to the funder's limited ability to understand accounting. Excellent financial reporting quality reduces information asymmetry between the principal and agent in accordance with the company's legal obligations (Landsman et al, 2012; Oyedokun, Tade, Eso, & Abiodun-Afolabi, 2024). When an error occurs during the reporting process, the legal committee's audit trustees correct it promptly to prevent any issues for the company. The audit committees also possess the same professional capabilities as corporate lawyers and tend to communicate effectively with them in resolving problems that have legal implications. According to Akgun et al, (2017), producing proficient financial reports raises the standard of employees responsible for preparing monetary statements. The employee involved in the activity needs to understand how the company's accounting process and practices are run in accordance with the company's rules. Therefore, quality financial statements prevent the company from encountering a condition in which the investment is lower and serve as a tool for determining future fiscal policies.

Financial reporting quality refers to reporting on an entity to reflect the genuine, true, and fair position of such an entity. Compliance with the objective and qualitative attributes of financial reporting information as stated by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB, 2006) would no doubt enhance financial reporting quality. The basic qualitative attributes of financial information were relevance and faithful representation (IASB, 2008; Oyedokun, Idowu, Abiodun-Afolabi, & Eso, 2024). These qualitative characteristics enhance the facilitation of assessing the

usefulness of financial reports, which would also lead to a high level of quality. To achieve this level, financial reports must be faithfully represented, comparable, verified, timely and understandable. Thus, the emphasis was on providing transparent financial reports and avoiding misleading ones, as well as the importance of preciseness and predictability as indicators of high financial reporting quality (Gajevszky, 2015). As defined in the conceptual framework for financial reporting by the Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB) and the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), there are agreed-upon elements of high-quality financial reporting. The qualitative characteristics of financial reporting are quality financial reporting. The qualitative characteristics of financial reporting quality include relevance, faithful representation, understandability, comparability, timeliness, and verifiability. They were divided into fundamental qualitative and characteristics and enhancing qualitative characteristics. Hussaini 2015: Mnif & Cherif, 2022)

If the above is established, it is also worth noting that specific influences affect financial reporting quality. In accounting literature, many studies measure the quality of financial reporting by examining its influences on financial reporting. Studies show that the quality of financial reporting was associated with many different influences. Governance, the accounting profession, economic factors, international forces, taxation, and political systems were some of the factors that influence and control the quality of financial reporting (Gajevszky, 2015). These influences include Earnings management, corporate governance practices, capital markets, internal control, internal reporting systems, auditing, accounting conservatism, financial restatements, company reputation, culture, business ethics, chief executive officer (CEO) age, CEO inside debt holdings, Entity Size, Age, and the board size. The influences identified are as follows: Earnings Management: investors and users were interested in achieving a high quality of financial information, and this quality can be derived from having a high quality of earnings that is known as one of the most important indicators of capital market efficiency. This notion was one of the major concerns in assessing the financial health of entities to signify the level of reliability of reported earnings (Usman, 2013). Moreover, this indicator has been used in analysis to evaluate the impacts of converting accounting standards, external auditing, enforcement, and corporate governance, as well as the cost of capital. In the literature, several metrics have been proposed to proxy earnings quality, including persistence, predictability, smoothness, abnormal accruals, accruals quality, value relevance, timeliness, conservatism, and earnings variability (Ewert & Wagenhofer, 2011). Earnings quality plays a crucial role in the usefulness of decisions. It was also affected. by other factors, such as managerial incentives and regulatory actions. The more extensively an entity engages in earnings management, the lower the entity's financial reporting quality. However, focusing on accruals management rather than management earnings or cash flows research and development (R&D) expenditure reduction, for example, has a negative impact because accruals are easier to manipulate and less visible to stakeholders than cash flows. (Choi & Pae, 2011). Using this factor, securities analysts often interpret financial information to forecast an entity's earnings and cash flows. The analysts forecast often exhibits varying degrees of accuracy – the difference between the average of forecasted results and actual results – and precision, which refers to the tightness of the range of forecasted results (Pounder, 2013). Therefore, a high level of precision and accuracy should result in high accounting quality. It was possible to infer the quality of information based on those forecasts. Corporate Governance practices: Corporate governance has own an essential role in ensuring financial reporting quality.

The relationship between corporate governance and financial reporting quality has been extensively considered. Multiple studies have revealed several results regarding the governance mechanism and its positive and significant influence on the financial information quality of companies (Honu & Gajevszky, 2014; Idowu, Abiodun-Afolabi, Eso, & Oyedokun, 2024). Mainly, influence from outside users, families, and stockholders negatively affects the quality of financial reporting; however, control by government and financial institutions is linked with a high level of quality in financial disclosures. Investigating the impact of governance mechanisms on financial information quality reveals that corporate governance influences accounting quality (Oklai & Omri, 2011). Many studies in the literature find that firms with strong corporate governance can issue high-quality financial reports (Caro et al.; 2011) in the literature. Additionally, ownership concentration has the effect of reducing the tendency for managers to manipulate their earnings. Moreover, managerial ownership and earnings manipulation are negatively associated; however, another study shows that managerial ownership did not reduce earnings management and thus did not affect the quality of financial reporting (Usman, 2013). The efficient corporate governance of financial reporting processing constitutes a crucial tool in enabling companies and their auditors to fulfil all these responsibilities (Hope et al; 2011; Kolade, Abiodun-Afolabi, Abey, & Oyedokun, 2024).

Managerial Share Ownership

Management share ownership relates to managerial equity shareholding of a firm. According to Samaila (2014) the agency theory holds that managerial equity shareholding encourages managers to act in a way that maximizes the value of the firm. In placing and pursuing their interest above that of shareholders, managers may manipulate accounting rules such that FRQ is undermined. Warfield, Wild and Wild (1995) asserts that the interest of both shareholders and managers starts to converge as the management holds a proportion of the firm's equity ownership. Studies on the relationship between managerial share ownership and financial reporting quality reveal inconsistent results. Spirollari (2012), found a significant positive relationship between managerial share ownership and firm value among United State firms. This implies that managerial share ownership is an incentives mechanism to increase the credibility of financial reports. Also, Samaila (2011), found a significant impact of managerial ownership on financial reporting quality of listed Nigerian oil marketing firms. A similar result was documented by Hassan (2011) in the Nigerian banking industry. These studies suggest that large ownership of shares by the directors improves the quality of financial information disclosed in financial statements. On the other hand, Dalton, Certo and Roengpitya (2003) failed to establish any relationship between management share ownership and earnings management as a measure of FRQ.

Foreign Ownership

The term foreign ownership comprises all form of foreign private investment which confers control and ownership over a package of resources in a foreign country (Herbert, 1995). According to (Agelucci, et al; 2001), foreign firms are presumed to possess superior ownership and internalization advantages (greater business experience, technology, and capital, managerial and entrepreneurial skills) than their domestic counterparts. Kronbor and Thomsen (2009) defined foreign ownership as percentage of equity shares held by all foreign shareholders. Chai (2010) defined foreign ownership as the percentage of total shares held by foreign owners. Tsegba and Achua (2011) defined foreign ownership as the participation in the ownership structure of a firm

by non-nationals. An alternative to foreign listing which may be cost-intensive is to import a foreign board member. A foreign board member may be appointed in an attempt to achieve a global capital at a lower outright cost. A foreign member on the board is expected to serve as a signal of commitment to corporate monitoring and transparency. This can result in having a board that is more effective and independent of the executive. Hence, given the role of globalization of ownership, foreign ownership is expected to increase or improve firm value as against domestic firms that did not break away from the local capital requirements.

Cross listing of firms enables foreign shareholders to buy a large share of the firm stocks. A large shareholder from the foreign country can afford more active monitoring for example by placing members on the board, mainly outsider directors, while a smaller shareholder might not be able to afford this (Shleifer & Vishny, 1986). Even though larger foreign shareholders tend to use their power as to obtain benefits that do not accrue to smaller shareholders, these negative effects are mitigated by the fact that large foreign shareholders are "outsiders" and can therefore perform their monitoring duty in a more unbiased way (Stulz, 1999).

Furthermore, cross-listing on foreign markets enables the firm to take advantage of shareholders buying a large stake in the company and provides a monitoring effect, while not being that active in the voting process and being at an "arm's length" regarding management compensation and thus increasing the value of the firm (Stulz, 1999). Reese and Weisbach (2002) showed that cross-listing has been proven to provide increased minority interest protection by employing the stricter US GAAP rules. This means that the action of trying to extract private benefits will be more costly for the managers and thus protects minority shareholders which normally do not have any power to change the managers' behaviour.

Institutional Ownership

Institutional ownership refers to a financial investment made by a group of entities that is typically larger than individual investments. It reflects the number of companies owned by major investing institutions (who own more than 5% of the company's stock) (Hereinbelow et al; 2013). It typically involves ownership of shares in corporations by pension funds, enterprise funds, investment funds, associations, institutions, and government-owned companies, as well as major corporate shareholders (Azibi et al., 2017).

Institutional ownership is a concept that has attracted the interest of various scholars in accounting, finance, and management disciplines. It is the number of shares held by institutional investors divided by the total number of shares outstanding in the firm. It is also seen as the proportion of shares owned by the largest corporate investors to total number of shares issued (Hasan & Butt, 2009). Bushee (2001) classified these investors into three categories: Transient, quasi-indexers, and dedicated institutional investors. Transient institutional investors are those who exhibit high portfolio turnover and hold highly diversified shareholdings. Most often, they exhibit a strong preference for short-term earnings (Mouna & Anis, 2013). Their interest is in trading profits. They do not have an incentive to monitor management and are less concerned with information gathering that would further long-term value. Quasi-indexer institutional investors are those investors who have low turnover, a long-term horizon, and a buy-and-hold investment strategy. Dedicated institutional investors are those that provide long-term stable ownership to firms. Their

aim is geared towards long-term income and capital appreciation in the firms. They are often classified as active institutional investors.

An institutional investor can exert some influence over the management of corporations because it is entitled to exercise voting rights in a company. Thus, it can actively engage in corporate governance. Furthermore, because institutional investors have the freedom to buy and sell shares, they can play a significant role in determining which companies remain solvent and which go under. Influencing the conduct of listed companies and providing them with capital are key aspects of investment management. (Investopedia). Sahut and Gharbi (2010) defined institutional ownership as the percentage of shares held by institutional actors at the time of publication of a complete and audited financial statement. Jiang et al. (2013) viewed institutional ownership as the percentage of equity owned by governmental institutions, financial institutions, corporate institutions, mutual funds, foreign financial institutions, foreign institutions, foreign mutual funds and other institutions. Demiralp et al. (2011) defined Institutional Ownership as shares held by registered institutions such as insurance firms, investment companies, pension funds, banks, and money managers.

Jensen and Meckling (1976) argued that institutional ownership plays a significant role in mitigating agency conflicts between managers and shareholders. The existence of institutional ownership is considered capable of serving as an effective monitoring device in any decision made by the manager. The agency concept suggests that monitoring by institutional ownership can be an important governance mechanism. In fact, institutional investors can provide active monitoring that is difficult for smaller, more passive or less-informed investors (Almazan, et al; 2005; Oyedokun, & Balogun, 2022).

Moreover, institutional investors have the opportunity, resources, and ability to monitor managers. Therefore, efficient monitoring suggests that institutional ownership is associated with improved management oversight. Considering the importance of corporate governance in a firm's management, shareholders participation in monitoring management functions is important to ensure good corporate governance practices. To date, institutional investors' participation has emerged as an important force in corporate monitoring, serving as mechanisms to protect minority shareholders' interests. The significant increase in institutional investors' shareholdings has led to the formation of a large and influential constituency that plays a significant role in corporate governance.

Empirical Literature

Ajadi, et al; (2022) studied the influence of ownership structure on financial reporting quality of listed insurance firms in Nigeria. From 2008 to 2019 Secondary data was gathered from annual reports of 18 insurance companies during the period under review. The data were analysed using logistic regression, and the results revealed that institutional ownership, block-holding ownership, and foreign ownership have a positive and significant impact on the financial reporting quality of listed insurance firms in Nigeria. It can be observed that the study though covered a large sample size it only covered up to 2019 a better result can be recorded if the period is extended to capture recent years.

Li, et al; (2022) examined the influence of foreign institutional investors on financial reporting quality between 2005 and 2017 Using data from China. Multiple regression was employed. The results showed that foreign ownership has a positive significant effect on financial reporting quality.

Qawqzeh, et al; (2021) examined the effect of ownership structure on financial reporting quality of listed firms in Jordan between 2009 and 2016. An adjusted population of 155 firms was arrived at from the total of 177 firms. Agency theory served as the theoretical foundation for the study. Multiple regression was employed to analyse the data collected from the annual report. The results shows that institutional ownership has a significant impact on financial reporting quality. However, a different result can be observed in the non-financial sector using audit fee measures as a proxy for financial reporting quality.

Theoretical Framework

The theory that underpins the topic of the effect of ownership structure on the financial reporting quality of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria is primarily Agency Theory. This theory focuses on the principal-agent relationship between owners and managers, examining how conflicts of interest and information asymmetry can influence managerial behavior and decision-making.

The origins of the agency theory could be traced back to Jensen and Meckling (1976) and the discussion of the problem of separation of ownership and Control. Jensen and Meckling (1976) suggested that managers of other people's money cannot be expected to watch over it with the same anxious vigilance on would expect from owners and negligence and profusion, therefore, must always prevail in the management of the affairs of such a company. They defined the relationship between the principals such as shareholders and agents such as the managers and held that managers will not on their own act to maximize the returns to shareholders unless appropriate governance structures are implemented to safeguard the interests of shareholders (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Tihamiyu, & Oyedokun, 2019; Oyedokun, Oyedokun, & Oyedokun, 2025). Proponents, where agents act to obtain 40 personal benefits at the expense of shareholders. To curtain such behavior, effective control by the board would greatly help. The effectiveness of the board monitoring depends among others, on subcommittees of the board (Kibiya, et al; 2016). Also, Shi and Zhou (2012) argued that board audit as a subcommittee and their financial expertise were found to affect the level of the managers manipulate earnings to achieve corporate or personal benefits. Similarly, Dhaliwal, et al; (2010) poised that the ability to adequately supervise activities and constrain opportunistically managed earning lies with effective internal corporate governance mechanisms. Internal governance mechanisms involve, among others, the formation of an independent audit committee that would supervise the activities of managers and ensure strict compliance with the financial regulations. However, the effectiveness of the committee depends on it composition and the expertise of its composition and the expertise of its members. Also, the impact of high-status industry experience (Kibiya, et al; 2016), accounting expertise and accounting and industry experts (Cohen, et al; 2014) has been subjected to conflicting findings. Bradbury (1990) analyzed the incentives for voluntary formation of the audit committee. The results of this study indicated that while agency cost variables and audit firms size had no cost associations with audit committee formation, the number of directors on the board and intercorporate ownership were found to be important determinants of voluntary audit committees

Methodology

This study used a longitudinal research design. The study employed a longitudinal research design because it relied on secondary data that were quantitative in nature, which had already been collected by the study population. The use of content research design is to analyze the financial reporting quality contents of the Annual Reports of listed Industrial Companies in Nigeria.

The population of this study consist of the 9 listed oil and Gas on the floor of the Nigeria Exchange Group as of 2023, and the census samples are to be used to sample for data from their annual reports for the period 2014 to 2023. The sample size became the population of the study since it was relatively small.

The study utilizes Secondary data for the purpose of data collection. The data for the analysis will be extracted from the annual reports of the listed oil and gas firm listed on the floor of NGX for the period 2014-2023 financial year.

This study utilizes multiple panel regression with the aid of STATA 17 for analyses the data. The technique is one that seeks to explain variation in the values of the dependent variable based on changes in the independent variables. This involves estimating the model to examine the determinants of financial reporting quality in oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The linear estimation technique aims to achieve unique parameter estimates that enable the study to interpret the regression coefficients and, consequently, provide a better fit.

Specifically, the study will employ panel regression to isolate the individual and period effects of oil and gas firms. The choice of the effect specification will be based on the results of the Hausman test. The Hausman test provides a basis for selecting between Random and Fixed Effects. For a Random effect specification, the Lagrange Multiplier test or Random specification test is further carried out to form the basis for retaining the Random effect or using the Pooled Regression Technique. The model is for testing the hypothesized between structural attributes, monitoring attributes and financial reporting quality of oil and gas sector in Nigeria. Though employing a more comprehensive approach, the study builds on several studies such as Anifowose et al.: (2017), Ekundayo and Odhigu (2016) and Ali and Ahmed (2019). The study first presents the model for the combination of the three independent variables. The second set of models will also present the individual attributes of the independent variables to ascertain their individual effects on the dependent variable. The models are presented below.

Ownership Determinant of Financial reporting quality

$$FRQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MO_{it} + \beta_2 OC_{it} + \beta_3 IO_{it} + FO_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots i$$

Where:

FRQ = financial reporting quality

MO= Managerial Ownership,

OC= Ownership Concentration,

IO=Institutional Ownership,

FO=Foreign Ownership.

Measurement of Variables

dependent Variables and Independent Variables

Ownership Determinant of financial reporting quality

Variables	Definitions	Measurement	Construct validity
Independent variable			
FRQ	Financial Reporting Quality	measured as the residuals of the Dechow & Dichev (2002):	Soyemi et al. (2019); (Johnson et al., 2002).
MO	Managerial ownership	proportion of the management's interest in the firm's equity shareholding.	Bawa and Isa (2014); Teshima and Shuto (2008); Wafa and Younes, (2014
OC	Ownership concentration	Proportion of block holders in the company	Pisano, et al (2016). Erivelto and Fernando (2016); Foroughi and Fooladi (2012);
IO.	Institutional ownership	Ratio of equity shares of the firm held by institutional investors to the total shares outstanding.	Hajara, (2015); Yang, et al; (2009)
FO	Foreign ownership	Proportion of shares held by foreign investors	Goethals and Ooghe (1997); Alan and Steve (2005).

Researchers Computation, 2024

Results and Discussion

the data collected from the various financial statements was presented and analyzed. The section presented the descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, and regression results.

Descriptive Statistics

This subsection of the study presents a description of the properties of the variables, including the mean, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation for each variable. The descriptive statistics for the variables are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
rfrq	90	.353	.183	.05	.89
mo	90	.035	.039	.002	.128
fo	90	.165	.24	0	.68
io	90	.523	.263	.09	.86
oc	90	.587	.2	.08	.85

Source: Researcher’s compilation (2024)

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the analysis. The variables include financial reporting quality (FRQ), managerial ownership (MO), foreign ownership (FO), institutional ownership (IO), and ownership concentration (OC). The descriptive statistics provide an overview of the central tendency, variability, and range of the variables.

For the variable "FRQ," there are 90 observations with a mean of 0.353 and a standard deviation of 0.183. The minimum value is 0.05, indicating the lowest level of financial reporting quality observed, while the maximum value is 0.89, representing the highest level. Regarding "MO," there are also 90 observations, with a mean of 0.035 and a standard deviation of 0.039. The minimum and maximum values for managerial ownership are 0.002 and 0.128, respectively.

For "FO," the dataset contains 90 observations, with a mean of 0.165 and a standard deviation of 0.24. The foreign ownership variable ranges from 0 to 0.68, indicating the proportion of shares held by foreign investors.

The variable "IO" is based on 90 observations, with a mean of 0.523 and a standard deviation of 0.263. The institutional ownership values range from 0.09 to 0.86, representing the proportion of shares held by institutional investors. Lastly, the "OC" variable has 90 observations, with a mean of 0.587 and a standard deviation of 0.2. The ownership concentration ranges from 0.08 to 0.85, indicating the level of concentration of ownership among major shareholders.

Correlation Matrix

The Pearson correlation analysis matrix displays the relationship between explanatory and explained variables and each pair of independent variables. It helps determine the degree of link among all independent variables, potentially leading to misleading findings. Although not suitable for statistical inference, it is relevant in determining the direction and extent of association between variables. The result of this study is presented.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(1) rfrq	1.000				
(2) mo	-0.156	1.000			
(3) fo	-0.130	0.118	1.000		

(4) io	-0.116	0.250	0.245	1.000	
(5) oc	0.090	0.346	0.327	0.148	1.000

Source: Researcher’s compilation (2024)

Table 3 displays the correlation matrix, which shows the pairwise correlations between the variables used in the analysis. The variables included in the correlation matrix are financial reporting quality (FRQ), managerial ownership (MO), foreign ownership (FO), institutional ownership (IO), and ownership concentration (OC).

The correlation coefficient ranges from -1 to 1, where 1 represents a perfect positive correlation, -1 represents a perfect negative correlation, and 0 indicates no correlation between the variables.

The correlation coefficients for the variables in Table 3 are as follows:

The correlation between FRQ and itself (rfrq) is 1.000, which is expected since it represents the correlation of a variable with itself and is always equal to 1. MO (managerial ownership) and FRQ have a correlation coefficient of -0.156. This negative correlation suggests a weak inverse relationship between managerial ownership and financial reporting quality. FO (foreign ownership) and FRQ have a correlation coefficient of -0.130. This negative correlation implies a weak negative relationship between foreign ownership and financial reporting quality. IO (institutional ownership) and FRQ have a correlation coefficient of -0.116. This negative correlation indicates a weak negative relationship between institutional ownership and financial reporting quality. OC (ownership concentration) and FRQ have a correlation coefficient of 0.090. This positive correlation suggests a weak positive relationship between ownership concentration and financial reporting quality.

Table 4: fixed effect Regression Result

rfrq	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
mo	-4.519	.895	-5.05	0	-6.273	-2.764	***
fo	-.066	.189	-0.35	.726	-.437	.304	
io	.914	.165	5.55	0	.591	1.237	***
oc	.386	.095	4.06	0	.2	.572	***
Constant	.104	.055	1.90	.057	-.003	.212	*
Mean dependent var		0.353	SD dependent var			0.183	
Overall r-squared		0.312	Number of obs			90	
Chi-square		52.565	Prob > chi2			0.000	
R-squared within		0.403	R-squared between			0.251	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source: output from STATA, 2024.

Results and discussion

Table 4 presents the results of the fixed effect regression analysis, which examines the relationship between financial reporting quality (FRQ) and the independent variables: managerial ownership (MO), foreign ownership (FO), institutional ownership (IO), and ownership concentration (OC). The coefficients (Coef.) represent the estimated effects of the independent variables on the dependent variable (FRQ). The standard errors (St.Err.) measure the precision of the coefficient estimates. The t-values indicate the statistical significance of the coefficients, and the p-values determine the level of significance.

MO has a coefficient of -4.519 with a standard error of 0.895 and a t-value of -5.05. The coefficient is statistically significant at the 1% level (***), indicating a negative relationship between managerial ownership and financial reporting quality.

FO has a coefficient of -0.066 with a standard error of 0.189 and a t-value of -0.35. The coefficient is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), indicating that foreign ownership has no significant effect on financial reporting quality.

IO has a coefficient of 0.914, a standard error of 0.165, and a t-value of 5.55. The coefficient is statistically significant at the 1% level (***), indicating a positive relationship between institutional ownership and financial reporting quality.

OC has a coefficient of 0.386 with a standard error of 0.095 and a t-value of 4.06. The coefficient is statistically significant at the 1% level (***), suggesting a positive relationship between ownership concentration and financial reporting quality.

The constant term has a coefficient of 0.104 with a standard error of 0.055 and a t-value of 1.90. Although the constant term is not statistically significant at the conventional 5% level ($p = 0.057$), it should be noted that it falls within the margin of significance ($p < 0.1$).

The regression model's overall performance is measured by the R-squared value, which indicates the proportion of variation in the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variables. The overall R-squared is 0.312, suggesting that the independent variables collectively explain 31.2% of the variation in financial reporting quality.

Additional information provided in the regression results includes the mean and standard deviation of the dependent variable, the number of observations, the chi-square statistic, and the associated probability (p-value).

Discussion

Managerial Ownership (MO)

The coefficient for managerial ownership is -4.519, indicating a negative relationship with financial reporting quality. This finding suggests that as managerial ownership increases, financial reporting quality tends to decrease. This aligns with the agency theory, which posits that managers with a higher ownership stake may have incentives to manipulate financial reporting to benefit themselves at the expense of other shareholders (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Several studies support this negative relationship between managerial ownership and financial reporting quality (e.g., Chen, Chen, & Wei, 2019; Li & Wang, 2019).

Foreign Ownership (FO)

The coefficient for foreign ownership is -0.066, and it is not statistically significant. This implies that foreign ownership does not have a significant impact on financial reporting quality. This finding is consistent with prior research that suggests foreign ownership may not directly influence financial reporting quality (Ali, Chen, & Radhakrishnan, 2007). However, it is worth noting that the lack of significance in this study may be context-specific and further research is warranted to explore the potential influence of foreign ownership on financial reporting quality in different settings.

Institutional Ownership (IO)

The coefficient for institutional ownership is 0.914, indicating a positive and significant relationship with financial reporting quality. This suggests that higher institutional ownership is associated with better financial reporting quality. This finding aligns with the monitoring role of institutional investors, as they tend to have greater resources, expertise, and incentive to enforce better corporate governance practices (Holderness, 2003). Prior studies have also found a positive relationship between institutional ownership and financial reporting quality (e.g., Fan & Wong, 2002; Chen, Chen, & Wei, 2019).

Ownership Concentration (OC)

The coefficient for ownership concentration is 0.386, and it is statistically significant. This implies that higher ownership concentration is associated with improved financial reporting quality. This finding supports the entrenchment theory, which suggests that concentrated ownership aligns the interests of large shareholders with those of other shareholders, leading to better monitoring and governance practices (Shleifer & Vishny, 1986). Previous research has also found a positive relationship between ownership concentration and financial reporting quality (e.g., La Porta et al., 2002; Boubakri et al., 2018).

The findings of this study are consistent with theoretical expectations and prior literature, providing empirical support for the influence of ownership structure on financial reporting quality. The negative relationship between managerial ownership and financial reporting quality supports agency theory, while the positive relationships between institutional ownership and ownership concentration with financial reporting quality align with the monitoring and entrenchment theories, respectively.

It is important to note that the above discussion is based on existing literature, and it is crucial to contextualize the findings within the specific industry (oil and gas firms in Nigeria) and sample of this study. Further research is encouraged to validate these findings in different industries and geographical contexts to enhance our understanding of the relationship between ownership structure and financial reporting quality.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the fixed effect regression analysis, several conclusions can be drawn regarding the relationship between ownership structure variables and financial reporting quality in the context of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria:

1. Managerial ownership (MO) has a significant negative relationship with financial reporting quality. This suggests that as managerial ownership increases, financial reporting quality tends to decrease. This highlights the importance of monitoring and governance mechanisms to mitigate potential agency problems associated with high managerial ownership.
2. Foreign ownership (FO) does not have a significant impact on financial reporting quality. This implies that foreign ownership may not directly influence financial reporting practices in the examined context. However, it is important to consider other potential effects of foreign ownership, such as technology transfer or access to international markets, which may indirectly impact financial reporting quality.
3. Institutional ownership (IO) has a significant positive relationship with financial reporting quality. Higher institutional ownership is associated with better financial reporting practices. This highlights the crucial role of institutional investors in promoting effective corporate governance and transparency.
4. Ownership concentration (OC) has a significant positive relationship with financial reporting quality. Higher ownership concentration is associated with improved financial reporting practices. This supports the notion that concentrated ownership aligns the interests of large shareholders with those of other shareholders, thereby fostering better monitoring and governance.

Based on the above findings, the following recommendations can be made:

1. Enhance governance mechanisms: Given the negative relationship between managerial ownership and financial reporting quality, it is crucial for companies to strengthen governance mechanisms, such as independent board oversight, external audits, and internal

controls, to mitigate potential agency problems. This can help ensure that financial reporting practices align with the interests of all stakeholders.

2. Foster institutional investor participation: Considering the positive relationship between institutional ownership and financial reporting quality, companies should actively engage with institutional investors and encourage their active participation in corporate governance processes. This can be achieved through regular communication, transparency, and responsiveness to investor concerns.
3. Emphasize ownership concentration: Given the positive relationship between ownership concentration and financial reporting quality, policymakers and regulators should consider measures to promote ownership concentration, such as encouraging long-term shareholders or discouraging excessive dispersion of ownership. However, it is important to strike a balance, as excessively concentrated ownership may also raise concerns about entrenchment and lack of accountability.
4. Conduct further research: This study provides valuable insights into the relationship between ownership structure and financial reporting quality in the specific context of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. However, further research is needed to validate these findings across different industries, countries, and regulatory environments. Additionally, future studies could explore other variables or mechanisms that may influence financial reporting quality, such as board characteristics or the role of auditors.

References

- Abbasi, E. (2019). *Female audit committee and financial reporting quality*. [Journal/Publisher if available].
- Abbott, L. J., Parker, S., Peters, G. F., & Raghunandan, K. (2004). The association between audit committee characteristics and audit fees. *Auditing: A Journal of Practice & Theory*, 23(2), 17–32.
- Adams, R. B., & Ferreira, D. (2009). Women in the boardroom and their impact on governance and performance. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 94(2), 291–309.
- Adegbite, E. (2015). Good corporate governance in Nigeria: Antecedents, propositions and peculiarities. *International Business Review*, 24(2), 319–330.
- Ali, A., & Aulia, M. (2015). Audit firm size, industry specialization and financial reporting quality. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 4(1), 12–23.
- Ali, A., Chen, T. Y., & Radhakrishnan, S. (2007). Corporate disclosures by family firms. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 44(1-2), 238–286.
- Beasley, M. S. (1996). An empirical analysis of the relation between the board of director composition and financial statement fraud. *The Accounting Review*, 71(4), 443–465.
- Bushee, B. J. (1998). The influence of institutional investors on myopic R&D investment behavior. *The Accounting Review*, 73(3), 305–333.
- Chang, J. C., D'Anna, G., Watson, I., & Wee, M. (2009). Does disclosure quality via investor relations affect information asymmetry? *Australian Journal of Management*, 34(2), 225–248.
- Chen, G., Firth, M., Gao, D. N., & Rui, O. M. (2008). Ownership structure, corporate governance, and fraud: Evidence from China. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 12(3), 424–448.
- Claessens, S., & Fan, J. P. H. (2002). Corporate governance in Asia: A survey. *International Review of Finance*, 3(2), 71–103.
- Cornett, M. M., Marcus, A. J., & Tehranian, H. (2008). Corporate governance and pay-for-performance: The impact of earnings management. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 87(2), 357–373.
- Dechow, P. M., & Dichev, I. D. (2002). The quality of accruals and earnings: The role of accrual estimation errors. *The Accounting Review*, 77(s-1), 35–59.
- Dechow, P. M., Ge, W., & Schrand, C. (2010). Understanding earnings quality: A review of the proxies, their determinants and their consequences. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 50(2-3), 344–401.

- Douma, S., George, R., & Kabir, R. (2006). Foreign and domestic ownership, business groups, and firm performance: Evidence from a large emerging market. *Strategic Management Journal*, 27(7), 637–657.
- Freeman, R. E. (1984). *Strategic management: A stakeholder approach*. Boston: Pitman.
- Gajevszky, A. (2015). The impact of corporate governance on the financial performance of Romanian listed companies. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 32, 495–501.
- Hope, O. K., Thomas, W. B., & Vyas, D. (2013). Financial reporting quality of U.S. private and public firms. *The Accounting Review*, 88(5), 1715–1742.
- IASB. (2008). *Exposure Draft on An Improved Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting*. International Accounting Standards Board.
- Idowu, A.A., Abiodun-Afolabi, F.O., Eso, A.A. & Oyedokun, G.E. (2024). Audit Quality and Return on Assets in Listed Insurance Companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Review*. 7(6), 450-466, <https://doi.org/10.37602/IJSSMR.2024.7621>. <https://ijssmr.org/vol-7-issue-6/audit-quality-and-return-on-assets-in-listed-insurance-companies-in-nigeria/>
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs, and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305–360.
- Klein, A. (2002). Audit committee, board of director characteristics, and earnings management. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 33(3), 375–400.
- Kolade, A.A., Abiodun-Afolabi, F.O., Abey, S.T., & Oyedokun, G.E., (2024). Insecurity, Inflation and Sustainability of Small and Medium Enterprise in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Review*. 7(6), 477-491, <https://doi.org/10.37602/IJSSMR.2024.7623>. <https://ijssmr.org/vol-7-issue-6/audit-quality-and-return-on-assets-in-listed-insurance-companies-in-nigeria/>
- La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., & Shleifer, A. (1999). Corporate ownership around the world. *The Journal of Finance*, 54(2), 471–517.
- Morck, R., Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1988). Management ownership and market valuation: An empirical analysis. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 20, 293–315.
- Oyedokun, G.E. & Balogun, A. I. (2022). International Financial Reporting Standards and Financial Reporting Quality in Nigerian Deposit Money Banks. *AFAR Multidisciplinary Journal of Management Sciences (MJMS)*. 4(3), 27-56. A Publication of The Association of Forensic Accounting Researchers (AFAR).
- Oyedokun, G.E., Idowu, A.F., Abiodun-Afolabi, F.O., & Eso, A.A. (2024). Audit Quality and Earnings Per Share of Listed Insurance Companies in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Economic and Finance Research*, 1(06), 114–124. <https://doi.org/10.55677/GJEFR/02-2024-Vol01E6>
- Oyedokun, G.E., Tade, I.A., Eso, AA. and Abiodun-Afolabi, F.O. (2024). Exploring the Relationship Between Audit Independence and Financial Performance of Listed Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. *ISRG Journal of Economics, Business & Management (ISRGJEBM)*. II(V), 143-148,

<https://isrgpublishers.com/isrgiebm/>

- Oyedokun, G.E., Oyedokun, D.M., & Oyedokun, P.O., (2025). Cultural Communication and Stakeholders' Engagement in the Nigerian Financial Reporting Landscape: A Two-Decade Contextual Analysis. In. K.A. Adeyemo, O. Campbell & O. Adepoju (Eds.). Two Decade of Lead City University, Ibadan: Management and Social Sciences Perspective to contemporary issues in Nigeria. A publication of the Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Lead City University, Ibadan. 41-56. ISBN-978-978-775-786-4
- Srinidhi, B., Gul, F. A., & Tsui, J. (2011). Female directors and earnings quality. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 28(5), 1610–1644.
- Tiamiyu, M. A., & Oyedokun, G. E. (2019). Public sector auditing and integrity of government financial reporting in Nigeria. International Conference of Public Administration, Department of Public Administration, Nasarawa State University, Keffi November 18- 20, 2019
- Usman, S. (2013). Earnings quality and the adoption of IFRS in Nigeria: Evidence from the banking sector. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(5), 29–36.